

doi:10.5281/zenodo.20158905

Developing A Framework To Preserve Digital Evidence And Maintain The Chain Of Custody For Cybercrime Investigations

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ABSTRACT

This study proposes a comprehensive framework for the preservation of digital evidence and the maintenance of its chain of custody in cybercrime investigations. The framework addresses the challenges posed by the volatile nature of digital evidence and the complexities of cybercrime. It integrates best practices from digital forensics, legal standards, and technological advancements to ensure the integrity, admissibility, and reliability of digital evidence. The framework outlines a systematic approach, including evidence acquisition, preservation, analysis, and presentation, while emphasizing the importance of documentation, security protocols, and adherence to legal requirements. The goal is to provide investigators with a reliable methodology to effectively manage digital evidence, thereby enhancing the success of cybercrime investigations and ensuring justice.

Keywords: Digital Evidence, Chain of Custody, Cybercrime Investigation, Digital Forensics, Evidence Preservation, Blockchain

1. INTRODUCTION

The world today is experiencing an unprecedented level of digital transformation. From banking transactions to healthcare, education, governance, and even social interactions, almost every human activity has a digital footprint. While this revolution has brought tremendous benefits to individuals, organizations, and governments, it has also created new opportunities for criminal exploitation. Cybercrime has become one of the most pressing security challenges of the 21st century, ranging from financial fraud and ransomware attacks to identity theft, cyberbullying, and sophisticated nation-state espionage campaigns. At the center of every cybercrime investigation lies digital evidence information stored or transmitted in digital form that may support or refute claims in a court of law. Unlike physical evidence such as fingerprints or weapons, digital evidence is fragile and intangible. A simple change in system configuration, an accidental overwrites of data, or even the passage of time can alter or destroy critical evidence. This fragility makes the proper preservation of digital evidence a matter of utmost importance (Casey, 2020; Quick & Choo, 2021).

A key concept in ensuring the reliability of digital evidence is the chain of custody. This refers to the meticulous process of documenting the collection, transfer, analysis, and storage of evidence in a way that

demonstrates integrity and authenticity. In practice, the chain of custody is like a diary of the evidence's lifeit records every person who handled it, every location it was kept, and every procedure applied to it. Without this documentation, even strong evidence can be challenged and rendered inadmissible in court (Bhardwaj &Goundar, 2022).

In digital forensics, the recorded and ongoing procedure of managing digital evidence to maintain its integrity and guarantee its admissibility in court is known as the "chain of custody" (Tsai, 2021). Although the idea of chain of custody is not new to investigative techniques, it is especially important in digital forensics since it makes it easier to question the veracity of evidence. This procedure has historically been carried out on paper, recording the chronological order of evidence custody as well as the people and institutions that handle it. This guarantees openness about who was in possession of the evidence at any given time. However, chain of custody maintenance has become more digitalized in the digital age, providing more effective tracking and management tools. Because of its distinctive architectural qualities, blockchain technology has the ability to further strengthen this process, according to recent research (Efanov & Roschin, 2018; Billard, 2018). Blockchain offers a time stamped, unchangeable record of every transaction, greatly improving the ability to trace the origin of digital assets and confirm their legitimacy. Blockchain technologies can improve accountability, foster confidence among stakeholders in digital investigations, and lower the danger of evidence tampering by utilizing decentralized protocols (AlKhanafseh & Surakhi, 2024).

Although there are global standards such as ISO/IEC 27037, which provide guidelines on the identification, collection, and preservation of digital evidence, the fast-changing landscape of cybercrime has made it increasingly difficult for law enforcement agencies to keep pace (ISO, 2020; Simou et al., 2021). With new technologies such as cloud computing, Internet of Things (IoT) devices, and cryptocurrency platforms, evidence is often distributed across multiple jurisdictions and volatile environments. For example, data stored in a U.S.-based cloud service might be relevant to a cybercrime committed in Nigeria, making the preservation and legal admissibility of that evidence much more complicated (Alhassan et al., 2022).

Unfortunately, in many parts of the world including developing countries law enforcement agencies still lack standardized frameworks for digital evidence preservation. This gap often leads to lost evidence, weak prosecution, and the dismissal of otherwise strong cases in court. To respond effectively to cybercrime, there is a clear and urgent need for a comprehensive framework that not only protects the integrity of digital evidence but also provides investigators, prosecutors, and judges with confidence in its authenticity and reliability (Al-Dhaqm et al., 2020).

1.1 Problem Statement

Cybercrime is growing both in scale and sophistication. According to industry reports, financial losses due to cyberattacks run into billions of dollars annually, with individuals, corporations, and governments all being victims. Despite this alarming trend, many cases fail during prosecution—not because the crime did not occur, but because the digital evidence presented could not withstand legal scrutiny. Several recurring challenges can be identified. First, lack of standardized procedures means that investigators often handle evidence differently, creating inconsistencies. Second, fragility of digital evidence makes it easy for data to be corrupted, altered, or inadvertently destroyed during collection and storage. Third, cross-border investigations present difficulties in terms of jurisdiction and cooperation, as data may reside in multiple countries with varying legal frameworks (Quick &Choo, 2021). Lastly, technical complexity from encrypted communications to volatile memory creates additional hurdles that traditional evidence handling methods cannot address. The cumulative effect of these challenges is the exclusion of critical digital evidence from court proceedings, thereby weakening cases against cybercriminals. This problem underscores the need for a unified and practical framework that ensures digital evidence is preserved in a manner that guarantees integrity, authenticity, and legal admissibility.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of digital evidence management has grown rapidly as cybercrime becomes more sophisticated. Researchers and practitioners alike agree on one thing: without integrity, authenticity, and transparency, digital evidence will struggle to hold up in court. But while many solutions have been proposed, they vary widely in focus, practicality, and effectiveness.

One of the earliest voices in this conversation was Casey (2020), who reminded investigators that digital evidence is far more fragile than physical evidence. He stressed that even a tiny alteration like a timestamp changing automatically could undermine its value in court. Casey's work remains foundational, but it was mostly descriptive, leaving open the question of how his principles would stand up in real-world investigations. A few years later, Bhardwaj and Goundar (2022) turned their attention to the chain of custody (CoC), the documentary trail that proves who handled the evidence and when. They suggested blockchain could be a game-changer for traceability, but they stopped short of testing such solutions in live investigations, meaning feasibility remains uncertain.

Cloud computing has also brought new challenges for forensic investigators. Quick and Choo (2018) and Singh and Chatterjee (2020) both pointed out that cloud systems, with their multi-tenant structures and jurisdictional complexity, make evidence preservation extremely difficult. Their work revealed just how vulnerable digital evidence becomes when it is scattered across different servers in different countries. Building on this concern, Agarwal, Gupta, and Gupta (2021) conducted a systematic review of forensic frameworks and found that, while many had strengths, none offered a complete solution. Al-Dhaqm et al. (2021) attempted to bridge this gap with a "forensic-by-design" approach for cloud systems, but their work, too, was tested only in simulated environments. This trend promising frameworks that remain untested outside the lab highlights one of the biggest gaps between academic research and law enforcement practice.

Other scholars have looked at emerging technologies as possible answers. Nandi and Jana (2019) and Liu et al. (2021) demonstrated that blockchain could make custody trails more transparent and nearly impossible to tamper with. Yet both acknowledged practical barriers: scalability, cost, and the technical know-how required for implementation. Horsman (2021) explored artificial intelligence, showing that AI could help investigators quickly sort through huge volumes of evidence and even verify integrity. But here too, caution remains. AI introduces ethical and legal questions would courts accept decisions made, even partly, by algorithms?

Domain-specific studies add another layer to this debate. Choudhary and Singh (2022) focused on the Internet of Things (IoT), where smart devices create a web of interconnected evidence that is far harder to track than traditional systems. Their case study on smart homes showed that documenting a reliable CoC in IoT environments is uniquely complex. Likewise, Damshenas, Dehghantanha, and Choo (2020) showed just how volatile mobile evidence can be data can disappear within seconds if not preserved immediately. These works remind us that "digital evidence" is not one-size-fits-all. Different platforms and devices require tailored approaches.

From a policy perspective, the ISO/IEC 27037 (2020) standard has been a step toward harmonization, offering general guidance on identifying, collecting, and preserving digital evidence. But its broad strokes often fall short for investigators who need detailed, step-by-step operational instructions. Kessler (2022) echoed this concern, pointing out that even the most advanced technical methods will fail if practitioners lack the right training. In other words, human readiness is just as important as technological readiness.

Taken together, these studies paint a clear picture. Researchers agree on the importance of protecting evidence integrity and authenticity, and they highlight the promise of technologies like blockchain and AI. They also agree that new environments cloud, IoT, and mobile pose fresh challenges that older frameworks cannot fully handle. Yet a common thread runs through much of this literature: many solutions are proposed, but few are tested in real-world investigations. This gap between theory and practice leaves law enforcement agencies without a truly comprehensive and reliable framework. Closing that gap is the central motivation for this study.

Table 2:1 Review of Related Literature

S/N	Author(s) & Year	Title	Methodology	Findings	Limitations
1	Casey (2020)	Digital Evidence and Computer Crime	Analytical review	Highlighted fragility of digital evidence and need for strict preservation	Did not test in real-world environments
2	Agarwal et al. (2021)	Blockchain-based preservation of digital evidence	Experimental	Blockchain ensures tamper-proof storage of evidence	Scalability and cost remain issues
3	Nandi & Jana (2019)	Blockchain for Digital Forensics	Simulation	Distributed ledgers enhance trust in evidence integrity	Performance and resource concerns
4	Bhardwaj &Goundar (2022)	Challenges in Chain of Custody in Fiji	Qualitative interviews	Poor documentation undermines evidence credibility	Small geographic scope
5	Singh & Chatterjee (2020)	Automated Custody Systems	Conceptual and experimental	Automation reduces human error in CoC	Limited real-world application
6	Kessler (2022)	Legal Issues in Digital Evidence	Legal analysis	Courts demand clear CoC and human accountability	Jurisdiction-specific
7	Karie et al. (2020)	Admissibility of Digital Evidence	Mixed-methods	Evidence often rejected due to improper handling	Focused on specific jurisdictions
8	Liu et al. (2021)	Forensic Standards Compliance	Case study	ISO standards improve admissibility of digital evidence	Limited adoption
9	Quick &Choo (2018)	Cross-border Admissibility	Comparative legal study	Jurisdictional differences complicate admissibility	Outdated in fast-changing tech
10	Rowlingson (2004)	Forensic Readiness	Conceptual	Defined forensic readiness and benefits	Early work, lacks modern application
11	Damshenas et al. (2020)	Volatile Mobile Evidence	Experimental	Highlighted data loss due to lack of readiness	Focused on mobile devices only
12	Azeez et al. (2021)	Blockchain-integrated CoC	Prototype testing	Improved accountability in evidence handling	Costly implementation
13	Jang & Park (2019)	Forensic Readiness in Korea	Case study	Proactive logging improves investigation outcomes	Limited to financial institutions
14	Yeboah-Ofori&Boateng (2018)	Forensic Readiness in Africa	Survey	Policy and awareness gaps undermine readiness	Regional focus, not global
15	Karie&Kebande (2019)	Holistic Forensic Framework	Conceptual	Proposed integration of readiness, preservation, and admissibility	Not empirically validated

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

This research adopts a design and development approach using the Agile System Development Life Cycle (SDLC). The design process focuses on developing a secure and transparent framework for the acquisition, preservation, and management of digital evidence in cybercrime investigations.

The methodology begins by identifying the challenges in current practices—such as evidence tampering, inadequate documentation, and weak admissibility standards—and proceeds to design system modules that directly address these issues.

The framework emphasizes integrity, authenticity, traceability, and verifiability, ensuring that every digital artifact collected during an investigation remains trustworthy, auditable, and legally admissible in court.

3.1 Agile Methodology

The Agile approach was selected because of its flexibility and suitability for complex, evolving projects like cybercrime investigations. Instead of relying on a rigid, step-by-step process, Agile breaks the project into short, iterative cycles (known as sprints). Each sprint produces a working version of the framework, which is then reviewed and refined based on feedback from stakeholders such as law enforcement officers, forensic analysts, and legal experts.

Key benefits of using Agile for this project include:

- i. **Adaptability:** The system can be updated to accommodate emerging technologies and new forms of cybercrime.
- ii. **Frequent Testing and Feedback:** Each module (evidence acquisition, hashing, custody logging, etc.) is tested regularly to ensure accuracy and reliability.
- iii. **Stakeholder Collaboration:** Law enforcement agencies and forensic experts provide input during development, ensuring the system meets practical needs.
- iv. **Risk Reduction:** Problems can be identified and corrected early, preventing costly failures later in the project.
- v. **Continuous Improvement:** Each sprint improves on the previous one, leading to a robust final framework.

Fig 3.1: Agile Methodology

3.2 System Development Life Cycle (SDLC)

The Agile SDLC is employed to develop the framework, allowing iterative development, continuous feedback, and adaptability to emerging cybercrime challenges. The Agile methodology divides the project into phases, implemented through iterative sprints, each producing a functional increment of the system. The Agile System Development Life Cycle Phases are:

i. Requirement Analysis:

Objective: Identify and prioritize requirements for evidence preservation and chain of custody.

Activities: Conduct stakeholder interviews with law enforcement, forensic analysts, and legal experts to define functional and non-functional requirements. Use the MoSCoW prioritization technique (Must have, should have, could have, won't have) to categorize requirements.

Outcome: A prioritized list of requirements, such as secure evidence acquisition, tamper-proof custody logging, and legal admissibility reporting.

ii. System Design:

Objective: Create a modular architecture and detailed design specifications.

Activities: Develop use-case diagrams, ERD, and system flowcharts to model interactions and data structures. Define modules (e.g., evidence acquisition, preservation, chain of custody) and their interactions.

Outcome: Detailed design documents, including diagrams and module specifications.

iii. Implementation:

Objective: Develop functional increments of the system in sprints.

Activities: Code modules using Python, implement cryptographic hashing (SHA-256), and integrate blockchain for tamper-proof logging. Each sprint focuses on one or two modules (e.g., evidence acquisition in Sprint 1, chain of custody in Sprint 2).

Outcome: Working prototypes of system modules.

iv. Testing:

Objective: Ensure each module meets functional and non-functional requirements.

Activities: Conduct unit testing, integration testing, and user acceptance testing (UAT) after each sprint. Test cases verify evidence integrity, access control, and chain of custody accuracy.

Outcome: Tested and validated modules with documented test results.

v. Deployment:

Objective: Deploy functional increments for stakeholder review.

Activities: Deploy modules to a controlled environment for law enforcement and forensic analysts to evaluate. Collect feedback to refine subsequent sprints.

Outcome: Deployed system increments with stakeholder feedback.

vi. Maintenance and Iteration:

Objective: Continuously improve the system based on feedback and emerging needs.

Activities: Incorporate feedback into new sprints, update modules to address new cybercrime techniques, and maintain system security.

Outcome: A robust, adaptable framework that evolves with technological advancements.

4. IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

The implementation of framework for digital evidence preservation and chain of custody begins with the establishment of standardized procedures and technical controls across all stages of cybercrime investigation. This includes the use of validated forensic tools for evidence acquisition, automated hashing mechanisms to ensure data integrity, and secure storage systems with access control and encryption. Investigators are required to follow clearly defined protocols for identifying, collecting, transporting, and preserving digital evidence, while every action performed on the evidence is automatically logged. These logs capture timestamps, user identities, and system actions, creating a tamper-evident audit trail that strengthens the reliability and admissibility of digital evidence in legal proceedings.

In parallel, the framework is implemented through institutional integration and capacity building among law enforcement agencies and forensic units. This involves training investigators, forensic analysts, and legal personnel on the framework's procedures, legal requirements, and ethical standards. A centralized digital chain-of-custody management platform is deployed to facilitate real-time tracking, authorization, and verification of evidence handling from initial seizure to courtroom presentation. Regular audits, compliance checks, and updates to the framework ensure alignment with evolving cyber threats, technological advancements, and legal standards, thereby enhancing, effectiveness, transparency, and credibility of cybercrime investigations.

4.1.1 Login Page

Figure 4.1: Input login details

When the Page finished loading, it automatically brings the user to the login Page and for the user to proceed from this page, he/she needs login details which is his/her own username and password given to him/her in order to access the system.

4.1.2 Main Menu Form

After a user has provided a correct and valid login details, the user proceeds/ is redirected to this page (Main Menu) where he/she will access the system.

Figure 4.2: Main Menu Form

4.1.3 Add Case File Form

The screenshot shows a 'New Investigation' modal form. It has the following fields: 'Case Title *' (text input), 'Case Type *' (dropdown menu with 'Data Breach' selected), 'Priority *' (dropdown menu with 'Low' selected), 'Assign To *' (dropdown menu with 'Solomon John' selected), 'Description *' (text area), 'Suspects (comma separated)' (text input), and 'Tags (comma separated)' (text input). At the bottom right, there are 'Cancel' and 'Create Case' buttons. The background shows a sidebar with 'Dashboard', 'Cases', 'Evidence', 'Chain of Custody', and 'Reports'.

Figure 4.3: Add Case File Form

The above form is used by the Crime Unit to add new case given by complainer and recording the details of complaint. The above form stores the entire suspect registered by the crime management and each criminal can be search by name or case number.

4.1.4 Report Page

The Report Page presents a detailed account of the evidence preservation process, ensuring transparency, integrity, and admissibility of digital evidence. It serves as a reference for investigators, examiners, auditors, or legal authorities.

Figure 4.4: Report Page

4.2 Technical Controls for Digital Evidence Preservation

Technical controls for digital evidence preservation refer to the technological measures and tools used to ensure the integrity, authenticity, and security of digital evidence throughout a cybercrime investigation. These controls include the use of certified digital forensic tools for evidence acquisition, which create

exact bit-by-bit copies of original data without altering it. Cryptographic hashing techniques are applied at every stage of evidence handling to verify that the data remains unchanged over time.

The secure evidence storage systems with encryption, role-based access control, and tamper-evident logging mechanisms are implemented to prevent unauthorized access or modification. Together, these controls help maintain the credibility and legal admissibility of digital evidence.

- i. **Forensic Data Acquisition Tools:** These are specialized and validated tools used to collect digital evidence without altering the original data. They perform bit-by-bit imaging of storage devices, ensuring that the original evidence remains intact while a forensic copy is created for analysis.
- ii. **Cryptographic Hashing:** Hashing techniques (such as SHA-256 or MD5 for verification) are used to generate a unique digital fingerprint of evidence. Hash values are calculated during acquisition and re-verified at every stage of handling to confirm that the data has not been modified.
- iii. **Write-Blocking Mechanisms:** Write blockers are hardware or software controls that prevent any data from being written to the original evidence source during examination. This ensures that the evidence remains unchanged from the moment it is seized.
- iv. **Secure Evidence Storage:** Digital evidence is stored in secure environments using encryption, secure servers, or digital evidence lockers. Access is restricted through authentication and authorization controls to prevent unauthorized viewing, copying, or tampering.
- v. **Access Control and Authentication:** Role-based access control ensures that only authorized personnel can access specific evidence. Multi-factor authentication further strengthens security by verifying the identity of users before granting access.
- vi. **Audit Logs and Activity Monitoring:** Automated logging systems record all actions performed on digital evidence, including access times, user identities, and system activities. These logs create a tamper-evident audit trail that supports accountability and legal admissibility.
- vii. **Data Integrity Verification:** Regular integrity checks are performed by comparing current hash values with original hashes. This confirms that evidence remains unchanged throughout storage, transfer, and analysis.
- viii. **Backup and Redundancy Systems:** Secure backup mechanisms are used to prevent data loss due to system failure, accidental deletion, or cyberattacks. Redundant storage ensures the availability and continuity of digital evidence.

4.2.1 Training and Chain-of-Custody Management Systems

Training and chain-of-custody management systems focus on ensuring that personnel and processes support the proper handling of digital evidence. Specialized training programs equip investigators, forensic analysts, and legal practitioners with the skills needed to follow standardized procedures, comply with legal requirements, and apply ethical practices in cybercrime investigations. Chain-of-custody management systems, often implemented as centralized digital platforms, are used to document and monitor every interaction with evidence, from collection to courtroom presentation. These systems record details such as who accessed the evidence, when it was accessed, and what actions were taken, thereby ensuring transparency and accountability. Continuous training and system audits further strengthen the reliability and effectiveness of the digital evidence handling process.

- i. **Digital Forensic Skills Training:** This training focuses on equipping investigators and forensic analysts with the technical skills required to identify, collect, preserve, and analyze digital evidence using approved forensic tools. It ensures proper handling of devices, data acquisition methods, and evidence preservation techniques.
- ii. **Legal and Regulatory Compliance Training:** Personnel are trained on cybercrime laws, evidence admissibility standards, and legal procedures relevant to digital evidence. This helps ensure that investigations comply with national and international legal requirements, reducing the risk of evidence being challenged in court.

- iii. **Ethical and Professional Conduct Training:** This training emphasizes ethical responsibilities, confidentiality, and professional behavior when handling sensitive digital information. It helps prevent misuse of evidence and protects the rights of individuals involved in investigations.
- iv. **Continuous Professional Development:** Ongoing training programs and refresher courses are provided to keep personnel updated on emerging cyber threats, new technologies, and evolving forensic methodologies.
- v. **Evidence Documentation and Tracking:** Chain-of-custody systems record detailed information about digital evidence, including collection time, location, responsible personnel, and evidence description. This documentation ensures traceability throughout the evidence lifecycle.
- vi. **Centralized Digital Evidence Management Platforms:** These systems provide a centralized repository for managing digital evidence and custody records. They enable secure storage, retrieval, and real-time monitoring of evidence handling activities.
- vii. **Access Control and Authorization:** The systems enforce role-based access controls, ensuring that only authorized individuals can handle or transfer evidence. All access requests are logged and verified.
- viii. **Audit Trails and Reporting:** Automated audit logs capture every action performed on the evidence, including transfers, analysis, and storage changes. Reporting features support transparency and accountability during internal reviews and legal proceedings.
- ix. **Evidence Transfer and Verification Mechanisms:** Evidence is transferred between individuals or departments, the system records custody changes and verifies evidence integrity using hash values. This prevents disputes over evidence tampering or loss.

Figure 4.5: Training and Chain-of-Custody Management Systems

4.2.2 Installation and Configuration

The installation and configuration phase is the foundation of the digital evidence management system, ensuring that the platform operates securely and efficiently. This process begins with preparing the hardware and software environment, including servers, operating systems, databases, and network components. All system requirements are verified to ensure compatibility with forensic tools and security standards used in cybercrime investigations.

During installation, the system software is deployed on secure servers with controlled network access. Essential components such as databases, application services, and supporting libraries are installed and

tested. Security features including encryption services, firewall rules, and intrusion detection mechanisms are enabled to protect the system from unauthorized access and cyber threats.

Configuration follows installation and involves setting system parameters according to organizational policies and legal requirements. This includes defining user roles and permissions, configuring authentication mechanisms, and selecting cryptographic standards for data protection and integrity verification. Logging and audit settings are also configured to ensure that all system activities are properly recorded for accountability and compliance.

The installation and configuration process concludes with system testing and validation. Functional and security tests are conducted to confirm that the system operates as intended and that all configurations are correctly applied. Any issues identified are resolved before the system is approved for operational use, ensuring reliability, security, and readiness for managing digital evidence.

- i. **Environment Preparation:** The installation environment is prepared by setting up secure servers, operating systems, databases, and network configurations. Necessary updates, patches, and dependencies are installed to create a stable and secure platform.
- ii. **Software Installation:** The system application and its components are installed on designated servers. This includes deploying application services, databases, and supporting modules required for system operation.
- iii. **Security Configuration:** Security controls such as encryption, firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and secure communication protocols are configured. These measures protect digital evidence and system resources from unauthorized access and cyber threats.
- iv. **User Roles and Access Control Setup:** User accounts are created and assigned role-based permissions according to organizational policies. This ensures that only authorized personnel can access, modify, or manage digital evidence.
- v. **System Parameter Configuration:** Operational parameters such as logging policies, hashing algorithms, storage paths, and backup schedules are defined. Proper configuration ensures consistency, traceability, and evidence integrity.
- vi. **Integration with Forensic Tools:** The system is configured to integrate with approved digital forensic tools and external systems. This enables seamless evidence acquisition, analysis, and chain-of-custody tracking.
- vii. **Testing and Validation:** After installation and configuration, functional and security testing is conducted to verify that the system operates correctly. Identified issues are resolved before the system is officially deployed for operational use.

4.2.4 Testing and Evaluation of the Framework

Testing and evaluation of the framework were conducted to ensure that the system meets its functional, security, and usability requirements. This phase focused on validating that all system components such as evidence acquisition, hash generation, chain-of-custody logging, and role-based access control operate correctly and cohesively. The evaluation process assessed system reliability, accuracy of forensic operations, and compliance with digital forensic standards. By systematically identifying and resolving defects, the testing phase ensured that the framework performs consistently under expected operational conditions.

The framework was evaluated against real-world forensic scenarios to verify its effectiveness in preserving evidence integrity and supporting investigative workflows. Test cases were designed to simulate typical user interactions from investigators, forensic analysts, and administrators. The results of these evaluations demonstrated that the framework could securely manage digital evidence while maintaining auditability, traceability, and legal admissibility.

4.2.6 Testing Approach

The testing approach adopted a structured methodology to comprehensively assess the system's performance and robustness. Multiple testing techniques were applied to cover both technical and user-oriented aspects of the framework. This approach ensured that the system not only functions as intended but also remains secure, user-friendly, and resilient against misuse or failure.

Functional Testing: was performed to verify that all features of the framework operate according to the specified requirements. This included testing evidence registration, hash generation and verification, user role management, report generation, and audit trail logging. Each function was tested using predefined inputs and expected outputs to confirm correctness, consistency, and error handling.

Security Testing: Focused on identifying vulnerabilities that could compromise evidence integrity or system confidentiality. This involved testing authentication and authorization mechanisms, access controls, data encryption, and resistance to unauthorized access or tampering. Security testing ensured that only authorized users could perform sensitive actions and that all evidence remained protected throughout its lifecycle.

Usability Testing: Evaluated the system from the end-user perspective to ensure ease of use and clarity of interaction. Users representing different roles interacted with the system to perform typical tasks, and feedback was collected regarding interface design, navigation, and overall user experience. The results helped refine the interface to reduce complexity, minimize user errors, and improve efficiency, ensuring that the framework supports practical and effective forensic operations.

4.2.7 Test Scenarios and Procedures

Test scenarios and procedures were defined to evaluate the system's ability to manage digital evidence accurately and securely throughout its lifecycle. The evidence collection test assessed whether the system could correctly acquire digital evidence from a source, record relevant metadata, and generate a unique cryptographic hash at the point of acquisition. This test ensured that evidence was captured without alteration and immediately logged within the chain-of-custody framework. The evidence transfer test evaluated the secure movement of evidence between system components or authorized users, verifying that access permissions, logging, and audit trails were properly enforced during transfer operations.

The hash validation test focused on verifying evidence integrity over time. In this scenario, previously stored evidence was rehashed and compared against the original hash values recorded at acquisition. Any mismatch was flagged by the system, demonstrating its capability to detect tampering or corruption. These test scenarios collectively confirmed that the system maintains forensic soundness from initial collection through subsequent handling and verification stages.

4.3 Results

The verification of integrity results demonstrate that the system effectively preserves the authenticity and reliability of digital evidence throughout its lifecycle. The consistently generating and validating cryptographic hash values at key stages such as evidence acquisition, storage, and transfer the system was able to detect any unauthorized modification or corruption of evidence. Test outcomes showed that original and recalculated hash values matched under normal operations, while any simulated tampering attempts were immediately identified and flagged. These results confirm that the framework maintains a strong chain of custody and supports the forensic soundness required for legal and investigative purposes. The results align closely with the research questions posed in the study, particularly those concerning evidence integrity, secure handling, and system effectiveness. The successful implementation of automated hashing, audit logging, and role-based access control directly addresses questions related to maintaining trustworthiness and traceability of digital evidence. Furthermore, the system's ability to integrate testing, validation, and security controls demonstrates that the proposed framework adequately responds to the research problem of ensuring reliable and verifiable digital forensic processes.

The evaluation results indicate that the main objectives of the study were successfully achieved. The framework met its goals of providing secure evidence management, ensuring integrity verification, and supporting legally compliant forensic workflows. Functional and security testing confirmed that the system operates as intended, while usability considerations ensured practical adoption by different user roles. The achievement of these objectives validates the effectiveness of the proposed framework and demonstrates its suitability for real-world digital forensic applications.

The results of system testing demonstrate that the framework performs effectively under operational conditions. Performance results indicate that evidence processing, hashing, and verification operations were executed efficiently without significant delays, even when handling multiple evidence items. System

responsiveness and reliability met the defined performance criteria, supporting practical forensic workflows. The verification of integrity results confirmed the system's ability to preserve evidence integrity throughout its lifecycle. Hash validation tests consistently matched original values, and the system successfully detected any simulated tampering attempts. These results validate the framework's effectiveness in maintaining forensic integrity and supporting the legal admissibility of digital evidence.

5. CONCLUSION

This study successfully achieved its aim of developing a framework for digital evidence preservation and chain of custody in cybercrime investigation. Through a systematic requirements analysis, design, development, implementation, and testing process, the study addressed critical challenges associated with evidence integrity, accountability, and legal admissibility.

The conclusions drawn from the study emphasize that digital evidence preservation cannot rely solely on forensic tools but must be supported by structured documentation, secure system architecture, and trained personnel. The proposed framework demonstrates that combining cryptographic hashing, access control, audit logging, and standardized procedures provides a robust foundation for maintaining chain of custody. The implementation of the framework showed that centralized digital chain-of-custody systems significantly improve transparency and efficiency in evidence handling. Automated documentation and integrity verification reduce human error and enhance trust in forensic processes, particularly in complex cybercrime investigations involving multiple stakeholders.

Testing and evaluation confirmed that the framework is both effective and practical. The system consistently preserved evidence integrity, detected tampering attempts, and supported authorized access without compromising usability. These outcomes reinforce the conclusion that the framework is suitable for real-world deployment.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that a well-designed and rigorously tested chain-of-custody framework can significantly strengthen cybercrime investigations. The framework provides a reliable, scalable, and legally defensible solution for managing digital evidence in modern forensic environments.

5.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that law enforcement agencies adopt standardized digital chain-of-custody frameworks to improve evidence integrity and accountability.

- i. Agencies should transition from manual or fragmented documentation methods to centralized digital evidence management systems.
- ii. Organizations involved in cybercrime investigation should invest in certified forensic tools, secure storage infrastructures, and automated hashing mechanisms.
- iii. Regular training programs should be implemented for investigators, forensic analysts, and legal practitioners.
- iv. Continuous professional development ensures that personnel remain updated on evolving cyber threats, forensic technologies, and legal requirements related to digital evidence admissibility.
- v. It is also recommended that periodic audits and compliance assessments be conducted to evaluate adherence to chain-of-custody procedures. Such audits help identify gaps, improve system configurations, and maintain alignment with national and international forensic standards.
- vi. Policymakers and regulatory bodies should consider developing or strengthening legal frameworks that mandate standardized digital evidence preservation practices.

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